

2-Hydroxyacetophenoneoxime-Thiourea-Trioxane Resin as a Polymeric Ligand

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Photo-decomposable low density polyethylene composition was obtained by adding nonionic, organic-soluble complexes of 2-hydroxy-4-methylacetophenone with metal ions¹. Polychelates of *o/p*-hydroxybenzoic acid-thiourea-trioxane polymers with various metal ions have been reported earlier² and their antimicrobial activities investigated³. A chelating ion-exchange resin, such as 2-hydroxyacetophenoneoxime-thiourea-trioxane⁴ (HOTT') may be useful as a polymeric ligand because of two moieties, namely, 2-hydroxyacetophenoneoxime and thiourea. We report here synthesis and antimicrobial activities of poly-chelates of bivalent Cu, Ni, Co, Mn, Zn, oxovanadium and dioxouranium with 2-hydroxyacetophenoneoxime-thiourea-trioxane (HOTT') polymeric ligand.

Results and Discussion

All the polychelates are coloured and amorphous in nature. They are insoluble in common organic solvents. The elemental analyses (Table 1) agree with a 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry.

Magnetic moments (Table 1) of the Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and oxovanadium(IV) polymers (1.96, 3.15, 4.46 and 1.81 B.M. respectively) lie almost in the range required for octahedral geometry. The magnetic moment of the Mn^{II} polymer

(5.33 B.M.) is lower than spin-only value (5.92 B.M.) which may be due to partial aerial oxidation of Mn^{II} to Mn^{III} during synthesis⁵. The Zn^{II} and dioxouranium polymers, as expected, are diamagnetic in nature. The diffuse reflectance spectrum of the Cu^{II} polymer possesses only a single broad band at 14814 cm⁻¹ which may be due to overlapping of the three transitions, ²B_{1g} → ²B_{2g}, ²B_{1g} → ²E_g and ²B_{1g} → ²A_{1g} expected for a distorted octahedral geometry⁶. The Ni^{II} polymer shows bands at 9009, 15151 and 21739 cm⁻¹ that may be assigned to ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{2g}(F), ³A_{2g}(F) → ²T_{1g}(F) and ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(P) transitions respectively, considering the distorted octahedral symmetry⁷. The Co^{II} polymer shows a medium band at 8333 cm⁻¹ and a broad band around 20202 cm⁻¹, attributed to ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(F) and ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P) transitions respectively, for distorted octahedral structure⁸. The reflectance spectrum of the Mn^{II} polymer shows three weak bands at 14814, 19417 and 22472 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g}(⁴G), ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g}(⁴G) and ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴E_g, ⁴A_{1g}(⁴G) transitions respectively, for octahedral stereochemistry⁹. The oxovanadium polymer exhibits three bands at 11904, 16393 and 25000 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ²B₂ → ²E, ²B₂ → ²B₁ and ²B₂ → ²A₁ transitions

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY DATA OF LIGAND AND ITS POLYCHELATES

Compd.*/ (Colour)	Metal% : Found/ (Calcd.)	Electrical conductivity		T ^a (K)	Activation energy (eV)	σ _o Ω ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹
		Ω ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	T (K)			
[LH] _n (Yellow)	—	4.58 × 10 ⁻¹² 1.59 × 10 ⁻⁸	303 443	338	1.332	4.79 × 10 ⁷
[CuL ₂] _n (Green)	10.88 (11.26)	6.65 × 10 ⁻¹¹ 1.15 × 10 ⁻⁸	303 403	323	0.689	4.69 × 10 ⁰
[NiL ₂] _n (Brown)	10.12 (10.50)	3.61 × 10 ⁻¹² 7.96 × 10 ⁻⁹	303 453	343	0.893	6.31 × 10 ¹
[CoL ₂] _n (Brown)	10.22 (10.53)	4.07 × 10 ⁻¹¹ 1.42 × 10 ⁻⁸	303 413	328	0.731	1.23 × 10 ¹
[MnL ₂] _n (Brown)	9.56 (9.89)	1.88 × 10 ⁻¹¹ 1.12 × 10 ⁻⁸	303 433	333	0.735	3.80 × 10 ⁰
[ZnL ₂] _n (Yellow)	10.96 (11.55)	2.06 × 10 ⁻¹⁰ 1.13 × 10 ⁻⁸	303 423	333	0.472	4.76 × 10 ³
[VOL ₂] _n (Green)	8.56 (8.98)	1.67 × 10 ⁻¹² 2.74 × 10 ⁻⁹	303 453	343	0.847	7.82 × 10 ⁰
[UO ₂ L ₂] _n (Red)	30.44 (30.89)	1.75 × 10 ⁻¹¹ 1.01 × 10 ⁻⁸	303 423	328	0.782	2.03 × 10 ¹

*L = C₁₁H₁₃O₂N₃S (HOTT' repeating unit).

respectively, for distorted octahedral geometry¹⁰.

A comparison of the ir spectra of the polymeric ligand and its polychelates shows a weaker broad band at 2720 cm^{-1} in the ligand due to intramolecular H-bond which disappears from the spectra of polychelates. This indicates the replacement of hydrogen of the phenolic OH group by metal ions¹¹. The band at 1270 cm^{-1} in polymeric ligand due to $\nu_{\text{C-O(H)}}$ vibrations increases by 15–20 cm^{-1} on chelate formation, confirming coordination through phenolic oxygen. The thioamide bands I and II at 1550 and 1500 cm^{-1} respectively, in the ligand, are shifted to higher wavenumbers by 5–20 cm^{-1} in polychelates. This supports coordination through nitrogen atom¹². The lowering of $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ ligand band (1635 cm^{-1}) by 10–15 cm^{-1} in the polychelates suggests coordination of metal ion through nitrogen of oximino group. The consistent appearance of $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ band at 940 cm^{-1} in both the ligand and polychelates rules out the involvement of sulphur in coordination. In the oxovanadium and dioxouranium polymers, strong bands at 960 and 920 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu_{\text{V=O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{U=O}}$ modes respectively¹³.

From the above data, the following structure has been proposed for the polychelates.

The thermal stability data of the ligand and its polychelates showed the order as : HOTT' > Co^{II} > Zn^{II} > dioxouranium > Ni^{II} > Mn^{II} > oxovanadium > Cu^{II} . The polychelates are less stable than that of the parent polymeric ligand, suggesting that there may be powerful intramolecular hydrogen in the polymeric ligand¹⁴. The decrease in thermal stability of the polychelates may be attributed to the catalytic oxidation of the parent ligand by the metal ion¹⁵.

The electrical conductivity of polymeric ligand and its polychelates was studied over a wide range of temperature. The electrical conductivity (σ) varies exponentially with the absolute temperature according to the relationship, $\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp(-E_a/kT)$, where σ_0 is a constant, E_a is the activation energy and k the Boltzmann constant. The logarithm of the conductivity was plotted against reciprocal of the absolute temperature. All the plots show greater slope in higher temperature region and lower slope in lower temperature region. In general, the two steps observed have

lower activation energy in the lower temperature region. This agrees well with the observations of Spiratos *et al.*¹⁶ that the activation energy approaches higher values at high temperature suggesting intrinsic conduction, while that at lower temperature has much lower values due to extrinsic conduction. The conductivity data are presented in Table 1. The electrical conductivity at room temperature in the decreasing order is : $\text{Zn} > \text{Cu} > \text{Co} > \text{Mn} > \text{UO}_2 > \text{HOTT}' > \text{Ni} > \text{VO}$. The activation energy decreases in the order $\text{HOTT}' > \text{Ni} > \text{VO} > \text{UO}_2 > \text{Mn} > \text{Co} > \text{Cu} > \text{Zn}$.

Antimicrobial activities : The effect of polymeric ligand and its polychelates on the growth of various microorganisms is given in Table 2. The growth of *P. fluorescens* is inhibited by the Cu^{II} and Co^{II} polychelates whereas HOTT' and Ni^{II} polychelates show partial inhibition. The Cu^{II} polychelate also inhibits growth of *B. subtilis*, *A. niger* and *T. longibrachiatum*. The growth of *A. niger* is also inhibited by the Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Zn^{II} polychelates. The growth of *P. fluorescens* and *A. niger* is stimulated by the Mn^{II} polychelate. The growth of *T. longibrachiatum* is stimulated by the Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and oxovanadium polychelates. Thus, results suggest that variation in structure on coordination effects the growth of microorganisms and may cause either inhibitory effect, stimulatory effect or reduction in toxicity of metal ions towards some microorganisms.

TABLE 2—BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY DATA OF LIGAND AND ITS POLYCHELATES ON THE GROWTH (%) OF VARIOUS MICROORGANISMS*

Compd.	<i>P. f.</i>	<i>E. c.</i>	<i>B. s.</i>	<i>S. m.</i>	<i>P. s.</i>	<i>R. m.</i>	<i>A. n.</i>	<i>T. l.</i>
[LH] _n	55.0	86.0	90.2	89.6	111.2	74.6	50.2	83.5
[CuL ₂] _n	5.0	110.2	12.6	80.6	110.1	68.4	9.6	0.0
[NiL ₂] _n	60.1	89.3	60.6	101.2	89.8	98.6	15.6	126.0
[CoL ₂] _n	6.6	90.2	81.3	92.4	60.4	78.6	3.8	160.4
[MnL ₂] _n	120.4	98.4	89.8	88.6	110.2	96.4	120.4	111.2
[ZnL ₂] _n	90.6	102.2	76.2	91.4	80.4	98.2	10.2	40.6
[VOL ₂] _n	94.8	96.4	96.9	98.6	88.6	111.5	96.4	120.8
[UO ₂ L ₂] _n	98.6	90.6	80.4	80.4	84.3	63.4	91.3	140.6

*Growth were compared with control and express as%, LH = HOTT' repeating unit; Bacteria : *P. f.* = *P. fluorescens*, *E. c.* = *E. coli*, *B. s.* = *B. subtilis*, *S. m.* = *S. marcescens*; Yeast : *P. s.* = *P. stipitis*, *R. m.* = *R. minute*; Fungi : *A. n.* = *A. niger*, *T. l.* = *T. longibrachiatum*.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were either of chemically pure or analytically reagent grade. DMF was used after distillation. HOTT' polymeric ligand was prepared and purified as described earlier⁵.

Polychelates of this polymeric ligand with Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} were prepared from their metal acetates and dioxouranium and oxovanadium polymers from their nitrate and sulphate respectively as follows.

To the solution of HOTT' polymeric ligand (0.02 mol) dissolved in DMF (30 ml), a solution of the metal nitrate (0.01 mol) in DMF (30 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring. The coordination polymer was separated on addition of saturated solution of sodium acetate in water (5 ml). It was digested for 1h in a water-bath, then filtered, washed with DMF and hot distilled water and dried at 60° for 24 h under reduced pressure.

Elemental analyses, electronic and ir spectra, magnetic and electrical conductivity and antimicrobial activity were determined as described earlier¹⁷.

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